

The Devi as Fatherless Daughter, Womb of Wombs, and Spouse of Her Son

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Abstract: In the light of an autoethnographic approach, I propose to evaluate a comparison between a personal tradition that was offered to me in a dream and the beliefs of Bengali Śāktism, considered through relevant textual traditions instead of contemporary ritual practice. Vamachari Tantrism as practiced by the Kaula and Aghori groups is the special focus. Three linked ideas form the hinges upon which my tradition turns, all of them shared with Bengali Śāktism. The first hinge is the idea of the Devi as Fatherless Daughter, the second is the notion of the Devi as Womb of Wombs, and the third is the designation of the Devi as Spouse of Her Son. The Devi as Fatherless Daughter is a notion that may be inferred from *Devi Gita*, where Parvati is born as the daughter of Himalayah and Menaka even though she is eternal and birthless. The Devi was said to have generated the Father already in Hymn 125 in Book 10 of the *Rig Veda*. The birth of the Serpent Goddess Manasa is also brought to bear on the subject. The Devi as Womb of Wombs is an idea that is also present in *Devi Gita*, where Parvati connects the practice of Yoga with inter-uterine life. The commentary of Bhāskararāya to *Devī-Māhātmya* underlines the same concept of Brahman as Śakti that the author of *Devi Gita* seems to refuse, but the latter certainly had in mind Mahaśakti as the Womb of Wombs. Tutelar deities of children such as Manasa, Shashthi, and Jara are much worshipped in Bengal and in their being Śakti they also represent the Womb of Wombs. The Devi as Spouse of Her Son is an idea that is found in *Devī-Māhātmya*, in *Devi Bhagavata Purana*, and in *Tripura Rahasya*, although the latter maintains an Advaita Vedanta approach that sets it apart from the other texts. In *Tantra Tattva* and *Maha-bhagavata* one finds other witnesses of the notion of Shiva as the Devi's son. The Bengali legend of Manasa and Chand bears witness to the conflict between Śaivism and Śāktism arising from Śaivist opposition to the idea and worship of the Supreme Goddess, never succeeding in suppressing the Śāktic faith but managing to force some measure of diminishment to the Devi's claims to power, silencing the voices proclaiming Śiva's filiation from the Devi as well as those affirming her being Mother, Spouse, and Daughter in order to impose rationalist abstractions instead of the fullness of human life. The Mother of Her Spouse is provided with an explanation in the sixth chapter of the *Caṇḍamahāroṣaṇatantra* and in Mahāsukhavajra's *Padmāvatī* commentary as the Yogini initiating the Tantric Yogi into the mysteries of sex, that may also include oral and anal positions. In the *Linga Purana*, Parvati the spouse of Śiva in her Kali form rages after killing an Asura on his behalf, and Śiva calms her by taking a child's form and being breastfed by her. In the mystery of the Goddess everything finds its fulfilment.

Introduction

Cheever MacKenzie Brown, in the introduction to his book *The Triumph of the Goddess: The Canonical Models and Theological Visions of the Devī-Bhāgavata Purāna*, stated:

...as my own mentor, Wilfred Cantwell Smith, has argued, the personalist nature of truth as found in Islam—and I would add, in the Hindu tradition—"itself requires that that distance, that nonengaged objectivity and neutralist observationism [often characteristic of earlier scholarly approaches to others' religiousness], be replaced with an existential concern, a wrestling with the implications for oneself. The very suggestion that truth is not an inert and impersonal observable but that truth means truth for me, for you, is challenging. Let us face the challenge." (Brown 1990: XII)

What follows is my attempt to face the challenge in comparing a personal tradition that I received in a dream with the religious faith of Kaula and Aghori groups of Bengali Śaktism. I am only concerned with textual traditions, not with contemporary ritual practices, because my own practice of devotion does not directly stem from indications provided by the dream tradition and is instead my own elaboration of the dream tradition itself. However, many of the texts being cited are sacred throughout India, not specifically a Bengali concern. There is no need to date the texts in this contexts insofar as the mere existence of worship of the Supreme Goddess is an adequate foundation for my comparison to unfold. In Bengal the Śaktas usually abstain from offering a sacrifice of eggs, meat and sometimes wine, whereas in other parts of India eggs, wine, and meat are all offered to the Devi. The main centre of Tantric practice in Assam is Kamatkhya, whereas in Bengal the Tarapith Temple is the chief focus of Tantric practice. It will be seen how, far from being a sterile exercise of self-celebration, the insight provided by the new perspective suggested by the dream tradition highlights some aspects of the Śaktic theology and ritual practice. On the other hand, the tradition provided by the dream receives support from adherence to a major religious tradition, thus lending credibility to its claims.

There are at least three connected concepts that constitute the cornerstones of my tradition and are coherent with Śaktism. The three concepts consist of the notion of the Devi as Fatherless Daughter, the concept of the Devi as Womb of Wombs, and the definition of the Devi as Spouse of Her Son. There are clear indications within Śaktism (and elsewhere) that these and related notions were cultivated in religious practices and theologies of the Devi/Goddess, which shows how fertile is the realm of the Divine Feminine, and how it needs to be cultivated evermore, as India as a whole and especially Bengal appointedly demonstrate.

A Dream tradition of the Goddess

In 2019, I was staying with my girlfriend Camilla at a bed and breakfast called "La Folaga" [The Coots] in Gavirate, province of Varese, region Lombardy, in Italy. Gavirate is a splendid location on the lake called Lago Maggiore, and many tourists travel there, not to mention the practitioners of water sports like canoe. In "La Folaga," I and my girlfriend made acquaintance with an Hindu young man, with whom we discussed religion. At a certain point, the subject was brought up of the Hindu story of the elephant of which every blindman touches a bodypart, believing it to be the whole elephant. This is an eloquent image, also recurrent in Jainism and Buddhism, of the partiality of every religious tradition, and at the same time of the fact that every religion contains at least a grain of truth. I was left with the desire to learn more about Hinduism and Tantrism.

In 2020, in Leuven, Belgium, at that point the father of Camilla's son Dior Dante, eventually my desire was satisfied as I delved into the *Mahanirvana Tantra*, the *Kularnava Tantra* and the *Tantra Tattva*, in the editions translated and curated by Arthur Avalon. I was awestruck by the revelation of the Goddess and immediately made aware of its revolutionary potential. I had always been aware of, and fascinated by, the divine feminine, but it had never occurred to me that the very origin of everything might be female. I had always conceived of the first principle as a neuter force or as a masculine God, and then

I realized that she is a woman. Never before had I been witness of such a profoundly lifechanging transformation as that which I underwent under the effect of such a revelation. It would take me years to properly process this change.

In 2024 I made a trip to Turin, Forlì, Bologna, and Naples in Italy, in order to present at Salone del Libro a book wherein a short story of mine was included and visit three art exhibitions: one on the Pre-Raphaelites, one on Witchery, and one on Tolkien. When I was in Forlì, one of the key places in my love story with Camilla, as I visited the City Park Franco Agosto, famous for being filled with bunnies, I saw her in full daylight even though she was not there. On the train, on the return trip, I started preaching Goddess to a gentleman who was quite a bit of a reactionary. It was not a premeditated move: words came by themselves, and I was surprised myself at having become such a zealous Goddess-believer. From then on, I have devoted myself fully to the Devi, whom I have often been calling Śakti, Sati, Parvati, Radha, Kali, and Saraswati. Other names from other traditions which I use are Shekhinah, Sophia, Isis, Hathor, Ishtar, Tinixochiquetzal, Bachue, Kaguya-hime, Nyoirin Kannon, Tamatori-hime, Venus, Liadan, Mary, Lúthien, and my own personal names for her: Anuka, Gwervaine, Phyllis, Velavyr, Eiriel, Lusina, Faebrielle, Fivilian, Tinicoatzel, and Sairil. There is a Sanskrit text listing all the one thousand names of the Devi, titled *Lalita Sahasranama*.

Immediately after returning from Naples, I had a vivid dream which I transcribed as soon as I woke up. It sounds like the foundational myth of a people, and yet it came to me from the unconscious, and was not the product of the conscious mind:

In the beginning was Goddess, whom some call Nothing and others Everything. And Goddess was Bride without Bridegroom, and Goddess was Daughter without Father, and Goddess was Mother without Son. And Goddess gave a kiss, and the kiss was God, and God was Bridegroom and Son and Father, and Goddess was Bride and Daughter and Mother. And from Goddess came God, and He was born in Her kiss as Her Bridegroom, and was Father to Himself with Her. In becoming Daughter of Goddess is becoming Son of God, and so She too was Daughter at the same instant in which she was Mother, although She was born in Eternity as Bride, just as God was born later in Eternity from Bride as Her Bridegroom. And Bride and Bridegroom were one from Eternity, although the Bridegroom came from the Goddess, and She preceded him in Eternity from Eternity. Mother and Daughter, too, and Father and Son, were one from eternity, although Daughter comes before Mother, and Son before Father, and both after Daughter and Mother. That this is true cannot be given to empty reason, nor even to blind faith, for it is a Mystery of Love. Now, since Daughter means Mother, and Son means Father, and Goddess and God partake in the Eternal Conjunction of their Sexes enjoying an Orgasm Without End, in the Mystery of Goddess countless Daughters and Sons were generated in an endless succession of immediate, painless pregnancies, as soon as Goddess and God were Goddess and God, and countless others continue to be generated in every eternal instant of the Eternal, which is the incessant generation of every conceivable infinity in all its possibilities and impossibilities, for even the impossible is possible in the Eternal. And there came infinite infinities of Goddesses and infinite infinities of Gods beyond all mortal conception, of which we know but a glimmer, and of that glimmer only a glimmer. And each of the infinities of Goddesses in the infinite united with her God and in the infinite generated infinite infinities of other Goddesses and other Gods, who did likewise, in infinite infinities of infinities of Love. And, faced with the infinite infinity of the infinite, God, who in His immensity is infinite like the infinite itself, felt small, because He truly comes after Goddess and only through Her. And God drew a Circle, and called it the Limit, and said that within the Limit only some things entered, and the rest remained outside. And Goddess liked the Limit, because it had no reason to exist, and as such it was new, and as such it was beautiful.

And Goddess created within the Limit a Triumph of Flowers, and called it Spring, because

indeed the Flowers already existed, but it was beautiful that within the Limit nothing but Flowers existed. But God said that the Flowers within the Limit would be only flowers, and would wither, and the Withering He called Autumn. Goddess wept, but then Hope reawakened within Her, and She revived a New Spring, and established that each Autumn would be followed by another Spring, until the edge of the Limit, which God called Time, ended.

Then Goddess asked God: "My Bridegroom, who will see these flowers? Who will smell their fragrance? Who will pick them to offer as gifts to those they love? Who will weave them into necklaces to adorn a breast, or into crowns to frame a face?"

And God said to Goddess: "Come to the Limit, my Bride, and love me, and give me Daughter in the Limit."

And Goddess told God: "Love me in the Limit, my Bridegroom, and love me in my body and kiss my lips, but remember that the highest form of Love is the meeting of the tongues and the joining of the hands and the intertwining of the feet, when thy heart enters my heart and the two are one heart beating at the same rhythm, faster and faster as love between us grows within us. And, when your key turns into my lock, your heart will explode within my heart, and from the falling rain of water and blood I will collect a drop that I will suck from my finger, and the drop will be the vessel that sets sail through my inner channels until its prow pierces Egg of Woman, so that Egg may conceive Woman, and from Egg Woman will be born. Infinite times we have done so outside the Limit, generating countless Goddesses and Gods, for indeed it is the highest form of love union that bears divine children and works infinite wonders and miracles. Now let us make Woman, our miracle child in the Limit."

Daughter of Goddess and God in the Limit was called Woman, and Woman was the most beautiful creature the Goddess and the God had ever created, even more beautiful than all the Goddesses who infinitely populate the infinite through the Love between Goddess and God, and indeed as beautiful as Goddess herself, so much so that infinite infinities of Goddesses admired her, and infinite infinities of Goddesses envied her, and infinite infinities of Gods venerated her, and infinite infinities of Gods desired her.

And Goddess said to God: "It is not good for Woman to be alone, but it is not good either that she have a brother. Let us rather give her Bridegroom and Son, just as I had you in the beginning, who come from me and from yourself."

And God answered Goddess: "Infinities of Gods desire Woman. Choose therefore who will be her Bridegroom."

And Goddess said to God: "Her Bridegroom is Man, but He will come from Her womb, just as you came from mine and from yourself."

And so none of the Gods ever had Woman, but she belonged to Man from the moment she came to the Limit, and by the will of Goddess, she kissed the spirit of her Bridegroom and her womb blossomed without the intervention of seed, and she gave birth to her Bridegroom, who was her Son in the Mystery of Goddess.

Woman and Man were happy for many Springs and rested for many Autumns, giving birth to many Women and many Men, and populating that Garden of the Limit that from then on was called World and Earth. And all was joy.

But one day, when Spring turned to Autumn, as had happened many times before, the Man asked the Woman where She came from. Woman, in her innocence, replied that She came from Goddess, and that she was Goddess herself in the Limit. But Man replied that He came from Woman, and did not know what lay beyond the Limit. So, without Woman and Man understanding, Limit placed a Limit upon Limit, and a glimmer of Infinity entered the Limit, which should not have entered. The seed of discord was called Envy, but Woman and Man were still innocent, and did not realize it was an evil, and thought that Envy was the Exceeding of the Limit. Indeed, Woman knew it, but loved Man, and thought that loving him was the way to heal him.

So Woman and Man had a son of Love and Envy, who was called Patriarch, and he grew to

desire revenge on his father, and so he began to say that woman came from man and Goddess from God. Anyone who contradicted him was subdued or killed, and the world darkened under the sword's dominion, and many flowers withered in Spring, though some began to bloom in Autumn.

Patriarch conquered the entire world and claimed to be God, and everyone forgot Goddess and God, even when Patriarch died and minor patriarchs came after him, who cared only about administering his domains and worshipping First Patriarch under the false name of God.

And Goddess asked God why He had allowed what was happening in the Limit to happen, and the God told her that a reflection of the Infinity had dazzled Man, because the circle He had traced when He had created the Limit had broken when they had entered it, and He had not noticed, and She had trusted Him.

And Goddess said to God: "Let us close the circle, and Envy will disappear."

And God replied: "But Man and Woman will die."

And Goddess said to God: "Let us open the circle, and Envy will disappear."

And God replied: "But Man and Woman will be Gods."

And Goddess said to God: "Then every Spring will open the circle, and every Autumn will close it, and Woman and Man will die and be Gods. Among Men some will recognize me in their Women when they hear their silver laugh or when they see their sparkling tears, when they passionately lie in bed together or when they selflessly put flowers in their hair, when their cheeks redden shamelessly or when they experience the motherly pangs of childbirth, and I will bless these couples with powers of divination and healing and I will open for them the way to immortality, even though nobody will listen to them. But one day I myself will enter the Limit, and I will be Daughter of Woman, and Man will remember that it is good to be born of Woman, and that God comes from Goddess. Thus I will heal Envy of Man."

And God, kneeling, kissed the feet of Goddess, for he saw his own Mystery renewed in the prophecy.

Subsequently, I wrote a song for Goddess in her Tinicoatzel aspect. I actually wrote several songs, but I think the following to be certainly among the most beautiful:

In the river of milk
There is a girl
Who struggles,
Who plays:
She is beauty,
She is refreshment,
She is caress,
She is treasure.

Tinicoatzel,
Goddess of Life,
Beauty of beauty,
Touch of fingers,
Open your hair,
Show your face,
Spread your aroma,
Let your laughter be heard.

There is no splendor
More clear than you
When your heart

Beats softly, dear,
While I embrace you,
Daring great pain,
You melt every ice,
You inspire every vein.

To you be the praise
Of every creature,
In you be the joy
Of every nature,
You are the foam
Of every torrent,
You are the foam
Of every current.

You are dew
In shy petals,
Jade stone
In streambeds,
Arcane glyphs,
Traces of shamans,
Winged griffins,
Blows of volcanoes

You arise stupendous
Of drunken fulfillment,
You rise tremendous,
You inspire rapture,
You are the drop
Of the honeycomb,
You are a spark
In a sky of candles

I would like to pay my homage to the rich Bengali heritage of the Devi by highlighting the shared features of the personal tradition that I received with Bengali Śaktism. I am aware that by doing so I may be suspected to have derived the contents of my tradition from Śaktism, but this is not a problem for me. On the contrary, I think that this is partly true. While I am not technically a Śakta, and I was not thinking of Śaktism when I received the tradition, it is true that knowledge of Śaktism prepared me to receive it and understand it and frame it in the intellectual and ritual forms that are proper to my personal theology and worship. In this sense, to say the least, I was inspired by Bengali religion and have to repay my debt, trusting in the conviction that mutual benefit can be derived for both parties from the exchange between my creed and Śaktism.

I wish to point out how three related notions that are key points of my tradition are coherent with Śaktism. These three points are the concept of the Devi as Fatherless Daughter, the idea of the Devi as Womb of Wombs, and her definition as Spouse of Her Son. The key sentence from the dream tradition is: “Mother and Daughter, too, and Father and Son, were one from eternity, although the Daughter comes before the Mother, and the Son before the Father, and both after the Daughter and the Mother.” In a Magar shamanic song from Nepal, *Naujā Gunāmī* [The Song of the Nine Witch Sisters], the “parentless daughter” Anākhenī is involved with the Creator Parmeswar in the creation of the world (Itis 2002: 28-29). Thus one finds a Hindu Fatherless Daughter Goddess. In the *Kurma Purana*, Śiva

says: “My womb is the great Brahman (Prakrti). I sow my seed therein and that is named Mulamaya (Original Maya). This universe is born thereof,” but he also adds: “The sages know that (Maya) is the supreme source (Mother) and I alone am the father of the various species in which all those forms (creatures) are born in this world” (Tagare 1951: 368). This means that the Brahman is the womb from which the Mother comes, the Womb of Wombs. In the *Devi Bhagavata Purana* Śiva says: “What wonder is there in My being created by Thee. O Mother! [. . .] Thou art always enjoying with Purusa, Thy husband. O Śiva!” (Vijayanand 2011: 173, 174). Śiva is both the son and the husband of the Devi.

The Fatherless Daughter

The notion of the Devi as the Fatherless Daughter transpires from her incarnations, and especially from her incarnation as Parvati. In the *Devi Gita* Narada says: “Relate to me, thou Great Divinity, how the Supreme Goddess, the primal energy of the universe, took her birth in the womb of Menaka as the daughter of her mountain lord Himalaya, fully possessed of all her divine attributes (in contradistinction to a divine incarnation with some specific attributes of godhead)” (N.A. 1910: 1). After Lord Himalaya and his wife Manaka, as well as the Great God Śiva, pray the Devi to incarnate, “on an auspicious day. Mena (the mountain queen) gave birth to an effulgent daughter, the divine mother of the universe, with a face like a (full-blown) lotus flower” (N.A. 1910: 2-3). As her father comes before the newborn child to interrogate her, she replies:

Know me to be the primal, supreme force, that resides in the Great Divinity (Mahes'vara), the embodiment of pure Science, the beatific treasure and the quality of manifestation (i.e., pure knowledge). I am the mother of the universe. It is I that ordain its birth, continuance and dissolution. Q Father, pleased with the mystic austerities which you have practised, and as a token of thy good fortune, I have taken birth in thy house as thy daughter. (N.A. 1910: 5-6)

When her father asks the divine child to show him her true form, she says that she is the “receptacle of all divinities” and shows him “her true image of Supreme Divinity”:

Burning with the effulgence of a hundred million moons, with her forehead crested with the crest of half-moon, carrying a trident in one hand and the other flexed in the posture of saying benediction, with clotted hairs dangling down from her head. Five mouthed, three eyed, with the serpent (the emblem of eternity) resting on her shoulder in the manner of a holy thread, clad in a leopard's skin, with the coils of the eternal snake fastened round her limbs in the manner of ornaments. (N.A. 1910: 7-8)

Her father then says: “O mother, show me another visage of thine” (N.A. 1910: 8), and she consents to his request:

Effulgent as the mellow golden light of the autumnal full moon, with a radiant diadem on her head shooting forth haloes of light in the surrounding space. With a pair of bright, shining eyes, and carrying a conch, a discus, a mace and a lotus in her arms. Decked with garlands of celestial flowers and smeared with pastes of celestial perfume. Her beautiful lotus feet, worshipped by the whole host of immortal Yogins, with her legs and hands, and eyes, and ears and faces everywhere. (N.A. 1910: 8-9)

Then she takes yet another aspect: “Blue as the blue lotus flower, decked with the garlands of Tulasi

(Holy basil) leaves, two-eyed, two-armed, with two feet, soft, and small like two red lotus flowers resting on two red lotus flowers. Her face, illumined with the beam of a gentle smile and beaming with the lustre of its inherent divinity, her body smeared with fragrant sandal paste and decked with ornaments” (N.A. 1910: 10). Then Himalaya hymns the Devi, to conclude by saying:

Fruitful is my birth today, today my penitential austerities have borne fruits, since, thou, who art the mother of the universe, hast taken, thy birth as my daughter. Great I am, I have realised the mission of my life, as thou, who art the infinite Reality without end or origin, hast born as my daughter through your sport of evolution. How shall I describe the good fortune of Menaka, acquired through the merit of her hundred births, since thou, who art the mother of the universe, has acknowledged her as thy own mother. (N.A. 1910: 15-16)

The motif of the creatrix incarnated as a human daughter is repeated on multiple occasions. She says to her mother: “Mother, both you and father have practised severe austerities and fervently prayed have me, the supreme deity, as your daughter. To crown those penitential austerities of yours with their merited fruits, I, though eternal and birthless, have taken birth in thy womb, O thou, the queen of Himalay, through my sport of evolution” (N.A. 1910: 17). Then Himalaya says: “O thou Mother, who art inaccessible to the gods such as Brahma, etc., whom the holy sages cannot reach by their thoughts, hast taken birth out of sport as my daughter through my exceptional good fortune” (N.A. 1910: 18). In the conclusion, Śiva declares: “O thou great sage, having thus heard the catechism of Yoga from the lips of Parvati, the Mountain King became liberated in life. And that Supreme Goddess, having thus discoursed on Yoga to the Mountain King, began to suck the breasts of her mother, out of sport as a common child” (N.A. 1910: 56). Then Śiva adds:

Having worshipped the goddess Shashti (the guardian deity of babes) on the sixth date of her birth, the Mountain King, with the members of his family, performed the naming ceremony of the child on the tenth day of her birth, naming her Parvati, (the daughter of the Mountain.) Thus the mother of the three regions, the eternal and immaculate Nature herself, having been delivered of the womb of Menaka, stayed in the house of Himalaya {lit. the abode of snow.} (N.A. 1910: 57)

And, finally, Śiva concludes: “Thus I have related to you how that Supreme Goddess, although Infinite and Eternal in her Self, took birth in the womb of Menaka out of her sport of evolution” (N.A. 1910: 60).

As it can be observed, the text contrasts repeatedly the stress of the Devi’s godliness with her human daughterhood. Her godliness is made evident in a series of epithets: “Supreme Goddess,” “divine mother of the universe,” “primal, supreme force,” “mother of the universe,” “receptacle of all divinities,” “Supreme Divinity,” “mother [of her father],” “mother of the universe,” “infinite Reality without end or origin,” “mother of the universe,” “supreme deity,” “Mother,” “Supreme Goddess,” “mother of the three regions,” “eternal and immaculate Nature,” and “Supreme Goddess”. Her daughterhood is evidenced by another series of appellatives: “daughter,” “effulgent daughter,” “thy daughter,” “my daughter,” “my daughter,” “your daughter,” “my daughter,” “common child,” “child,” and “daughter of the mountain.” The contrast is sharpened in two occurrences by concessive clauses: “though eternal and birthless,” “although Infinite and Eternal in her Self.” Her being called “mother” by her parents, several times, is telling, further highlighting the contrast. The contrast, and the concessive clauses, demonstrate the fact that the Devi cannot have a father nor a mother: she *is* Mother.

After all, already in Hymn 125 from Book 10 in the *Rig Veda* the Devi was praised as the Father’s Mother: “I am the Queen, the gatherer-up of treasures, most thoughtful, first of those who merit worship. [. . .] On the world’s summit I bring forth the Father: my home is in the waters, in the ocean. Thence I

extend o'er all existing creatures, and touch even yonder heaven with my forehead. I breathe a strong breath like the wind and tempest, the while I hold together all existence. Beyond this wide earth and beyond the heavens I have become so mighty in my grandeur" (Griffith 1897: 571-572).

Nonetheless, she is also Daughter, meaning that in her essence she holds the potentiality of motherhood, not its enactment. In this sense, she can be Daughter and Child without needing parents. She can be the parentless daughter of the Nepali tale. She can be the Fatherless Daughter of my tradition.

In Bengal Manasa Devi is much worshipped. She is the Serpent Goddess invoked for protection from snakes and to heal snake bites. It is first in the *Puranas* that her birth is related. Sage Kashyapa is her father, not Shiva as in the later *Mangalkavyas*. In a time when serpents and reptiles were creating havoc on the Earth, Kashyapa made the goddess Manasa from his mind. She was made the presiding deity of snakes and reptiles by Brahma. Manasa got control over the earth by virtue of the recitation of mantras. Manasa then worshipped the god Shiva, who told her to propitiate the god Krishna. Since he was pleased, Krishna conceded to Manasa divine Siddhi powers and worshipped her in a ritual, so that she was made an established goddess (Sharma 2005: 38-40).

The *Manasa Vijaya* relates another tale concerning Manasa's birth. Manasa was born when Śiva's seed touched a statue of a girl that had been sculpted by Vasuki's mother. Vasuki accepted Manasa as his sister, and put her in charge of the poison produced when King Prithu milked the Earth as though it were a cow. When Śiva saw Manasa, he was attracted to her, but she proved to him that he was her father. Śiva took Manasa to his home but his wife, Chandi, was jealous of Manasa, fearing that she might be Śiva's concubine or co-wife. As a consequence, Chandi gratuitously offended Manasa and burnt her left eye, making her half-blind. When Śiva lost his sense because of the ingestion of poison, Manasa cured him. It also happened once that Chandi kicked Manasa, and out of spite Manasa rendered Chandi senseless with a glance of her poison eye. Eventually, Śiva got tired of the endless dispute between Manasa and Chandi, and so Śiva left Manasa under a tree, although he also created a companion for her that rose from his tears of regret, called Neto or Netā. It was the sage Jaratkaru who later married Manasa, but Chandi had to ruin even Manasa's wedding night. Chandi advised Manasa to wear snake ornaments and then threw a frog in the bridal chamber, causing the snakes to run around the. Jaratkaru, terrified, ran away from the house, but after a few days, he joined his spouse once more and their son Astika was born (McDaniel 2004: 149-150).

It can be noticed from these legends how uncertain is Manasa's parenthood. In the *Puranas* her father is Kashyapa, and she is born from his mind. In the *Mangalkavyas* she is the daughter of Śiva, but she was created by his seed when it touched the statue of a beautiful girl. It seems clear that she is a daughter, but she has no mother and the legends have to explain this fact by tributing Kashyapa or Śiva with the power to create human life out of their own thoughts or out of a statue. However, removing the mother, also the father is removed, which is coherent with the fact that Śiva expels her from his house, *de facto* disowning her. Kashyapa does not even need to do so because they are only tied in their minds. Manasa's father either repudiates her or is tied to her only on the subtlest level, which properly makes Manasa fatherless.

It follows that it is certainly acceptable to consider Manasa Devi a Fatherless Daughter in the same sense as Parvati in *Devi Gita*.

In the sixth chapter of the Tantric Buddhist *Caṇḍamahāroṣaṇatantra*, one finds a related notion according to which mother and daughter are both representatives of the Devi and as a consequence acceptable partners of the Tantric:

Mother, daughter, sister, niece, and any other female relative, as well as a Ḍombinī, [the] female [relative of a] Brahmin, Caṇḍālī, dancer, dyer, and prostitute; holy woman, yoginī, and kāpālīnī

as well—Or else, whatever he may find fashioned into a woman’s figure: these he should serve in the proper way without disclosure. (Grimes and Szántó 2018)

In Mahāsukhavajra’s *Padmāvātī* commentary on the sixth chapter of the *Caṇḍamahāroṣaṇatantra* one finds an explanation of what the terms in the aforecited passage mean precisely:

Among these [mentioned consorts], mother can mean birth mother, stepmother, maternal aunt, or the wife of the master. Daughter can mean fathered daughter, brother’s daughter, the daughter from a previous marriage of a woman brought into wedlock together with her, or the daughter of the master. Sister can mean one related by blood, the daughter of a maternal aunt, or the daughter of the master. Niece means the daughter of any of these [previously listed]. Any other means those [different] from the four [just mentioned], who are defined below. (Grimes and Szántó 2018)

In a footnote, Grimes and Szántó add an interesting comment:

What Mahāsukhavajra has in mind here is most likely a passage in Kṛṣṇācārya’s commentary of the *Hevajratantra*, the *Yogaratnamālā*, where the *Buddhakaṇḍikatantra* is quoted [. . .]. “The words beginning with ‘Mother’ denote the five sense faculties. Those should be propitiated with the five objects of desire, viz. sound, sight, taste, etc. For there (i.e. in the *gaṇacakra*) it is this, which is the suitable unsurpassed worship of the goddesses. Now, if one were to ask: ‘How is it that [the words] mother, etc. [denote] the eyes, etc.?’ As it is taught in the *yoginītantra* [called] the *Buddhakaṇḍika*: The sister is the eye, the niece is the ear, the birth mother is the nose, the daughter is the tongue, the mind [here: the sense faculty of the body, i.e. of touch] is the wife.” While Mahāsukhavajra strongly disapproves of this interpretation, he seeks to defend the authority of both scripture and co-exegete by claiming that they are shielding the truth from those unprepared. (Grimes and Szántó 2018)

It will be shown later how the chief tendency prevailing in Bengali religious practices is the personalization of divinities, and especially female divinities, against allegorizing interpretations like the one proposed in the *Buddhakaṇḍikatantra*. Also in this case, obviously, the list of candidates for partnership with a Yogi in Tantric practices refers to categories of actual people, but it can still be observed that all senses are involved in lovemaking, thus making the boundaries between the categories synaesthetically shift also in this sense. Besides, the most important senses involved are taste and touch, so daughter and wife, which is coherent with my dream tradition of the Fatherless Daughter who is also (originally) the Groomless Bride, then to beget the God in her kiss and turning into his Bride.

The Womb of Wombs

The Devi’s discourse on Yoga to Himalaya in *Devi Gita* is introduced by a detailed description of the process of gestation of the fetus in its mother’s uterus, month after month, which is concluded by the description of the ninth month:

In the ninth month of gestation the child becomes endued with Self-consciousness. It grows within the womb of its mother, nourished by the essence of the ingested food of its mother. Through the dynamics of its acts of prior existence the child, although it suffers an intense pain in the womb, does not meet with its death. In bitter anguish, recollecting the deeds of its prior existence, it reflects in its mind and speaks to itself as follows,—“Thus having suffered this

intense pain and again born in the world, unlawfully I have earned wealth for the support of my relations and dependants. Oh, I have never cared to worship Durga, the goddess that dissipates all misery. Oh, if ever I am relieved of this agony of inter-uterine life, I shall solely resort to Durga and never suffer myself to be associated with the (ephemeral) concerns of this mundane existence” (N.A. 1910: 39-41)

The connection between this description of inter-uterine life and Yoga is made clear in a subsequent passage: “Liberation falls not to the portion of those who are addicted to the things of the world. Hence, by renouncing the pleasures of the world with discrimination and right knowledge, recollect the misery of inter-uterine existence and learn to be apathetic to the concerns of life, whereby an unflinching devotion to me, Supreme Brahma, will be engendered” (N.A. 1910: 44).

The key to interpret the passage is offered later yet, when the Devi explains her own nature as Maya, Śiva, Śakti, and Supreme Brahma (Brahman):

O Great King, those, who are enchanted by my illusive energy, know not my Secondless image, which runs through all. Those, who worship me, the Illusion that has fathered this universe, (Maya—lit. Nescience), are enabled, O Father, to surmount (penetrate through) this phenomenal garb of Self, which it has wilfully donned for the purposes of creation. I have divided my Self, O thou, the King of Mountains, into two halves; one, the type of manhood; and the other, of femininity. Śiva is the perfect prototype of man, Śakti the prototype of perfect femininity, the supreme female. Yogins, seers of the absolute truth call me, O Great King, as composed of Śiva and Śakti, the Supreme Brahma, the absolutely Supreme entity by the nature of my own Self. (N.A. 1910: 48-49)

The Womb of Wombs is Brahman, the Undifferentiated Absolute. However, the author of the *Devi Gita* conceives of this Absolute as female, a primordial, more essential femininity that precedes femininity as we commonly experience it as well as masculinity. This view is adumbrated in the thought of the Tantric Bhāskaraṛāya, “a South Indian Rig Veda Brahman of the Viśvāmitra-gotra, born in the Maharashtra village of Thanuja, raised in the town of Bhaga, then educated at his father's instance in Varanasi” (Coburn 1991: 122). In order to explain his views, Thomas Coburn premits:

One of the major points of contention in Indian philosophy, crisply dividing the major schools, pertains to theories of causation. Some have affirmed that effects exist independent of their causes, that when something "new" is created, it is ontologically distinct from its causes. Known as *asatkāryavāda* ("the view of non-(pre)existing effects"), it is the view held by Buddhists and the schools of Mīmamsa and Nyaya-Vaiśeṣika. Against this is the position, most often associated with the schools of Sāṃkhya and Advaita, which affirms that effects preexist in their cause, that "an effect ... is nothing but the cause itself, albeit seen in a different form or state." This is known as *satkāryavāda*, "the view of (pre)existing effects." Among the proponents of such a view, there is a crucial further distinction, between (1) those who see effect as an actual transformation (*pariṇāma*) of an underlying substratum, and (2) those who see it as a mere appearance (*vivarta*), a superimposition on an underlying substratum. The former of these sees creation as a process of evolution or unfolding or exfoliation, as in Sāṃkhya's understanding of the evolution of the primordial *prakṛti*. The other position, usually associated with Sankara's non-dual (*advaita*) Vedānta, affirms that the one reality of Brahman may be looked at from two different points of view: (1) from the empirical perspective, where it looks as if Brahman (with attributes: *saguna*) undergoes evolution into diversity, and (2) from the higher, mystically intuitive perspective where only Brahman (without attributes: *nirguna*) exists. The empirical perspective is here characterized by *māyā*, "illusion," by distinction of subject from object, a distinction that is superimposed on the (ultimately) true state of affairs. The empirical perspective, however, is not

permanent, for the experience of mystical union-what Deutsch calls "the Brahman experience" overcomes or sublates all differentiation. Ultimately, and knowledgeably seen, only Brahman exists. (Coburn 1991: 128)

Bhāskararāya was a follower of Sankara, yet he maintained the *pariṇāma* position of the actual transformation enacted by the cause on a substance through its effects. This is possible because, although Coburn did not state so, undoubtedly Bhāskararāya, like the author of *Devi Gita*, identified Brahman and Maya. In his *Lalita Sahasranama with Bhāskararāya's Commentary*, Bhāskararāya identifies Brahman as the Supreme Śiva with Savitri the Supreme Śakti: "699. Savitri. The Creator of the universe i.e. the Supreme Śiva whose wife she is" (Sastry 1925: 261). In another passage, one reads: "The Holy Mother. Srimata. [. . .] Or, Srumata: Sri Lakshmi or Sarasvati and *mata*, the mother of Lakshmi and Sarasvati [. . .]. Hence, Srimata does not mean the wife of Rudra, the equal of Sarasvati or Lakshmi, but the Creator of the three, the spouse of Paraśiva, the Great Mother (*Parā Bhattārikā*)" (Sastry 1925: 40).

Undifferentiated Absolute of pure potentialities is nothing but the illusion of unfulfilment, that the unfolding of creation (what is usually considered to be Maya) eventually dissipates by fulfilling. This is the reason why the Devi needs to incarnate: she cannot remain a sheer potentiality, she needs fulfilment. Nonetheless, she also needs to reunite to the realm of potentialities to which she belongs: this is why Sati has to die. But the *Devī-Māhātmya* depicts the Devi as emanating and reabsorbing within herself at will several forms that bear the names of Hindu Goddesses like Kali and others.

Coburn then explains the position of Bhāskararāya in terms of Brahman/Śakti. This terminology is foreign to the *Devi Gita*, wherein the only mention of Śakti is the passage aforesaid where the Devi says that she divided herself into Śiva and Śakti. However, it is possible to conceive that both Bhāskararāya and the author of the *Devi Gita* thought of Brahman as the same as Mahaśakti, that divided herself into Śakti and Śiva.

[W]hen Bhāskararāya does describe the evolution of the original, undifferentiated reality of Brahman/Śakti into the manifest diversity of the world, he does so with two different emphases. One underscores the binary division that Brahman undergoes, into male or Śiva and female or Śakti.

[quote] ... by Its own conscious will (*icchā-*), act (*kriyā-*), and knowledge (*jñānaśakti*) as well as for Its own pleasure (ananda) and for the pleasure of the beings it created, the Absolute Brahman took the form of binary divinity. Through the Deity's bifurcation into masculine and feminine aspects the multifarious names and forms of the Universe gradually devolve. [end quote]

The other perspective emphasizes the triadic nature of this creative process. It takes note of the threefold appearance of Śakti as desire (*icchā*), action (*kriyā/kṛti*), and knowledge (*jñāna*), hence the appropriateness of the name Tripura ("Three Cities") to name the goddess. It goes on to correlate this trifurcation with various anthropomorphic forms and with the triangular structure of the Sricakra. In neither the dyadic nor the triadic case, we may note, is the gender of deity a matter of critical importance. Although, for Bhāskararāya, it is the feminine principle that actualizes the divine impulse to creative self-manifestation, he is not primarily concerned to argue this point, for "the form in which she is worshipped is a matter of one's [own] tradition." What is critical is the immediate access to ultimacy that is provided to human beings by the ontological continuum, whose agent and (from another angle) whose material substance is Śakti. (Coburn 1991: 129)

The notion of ontological continuum certainly presupposes the coincidence of Brahman and (Maha)Śakti, a prospect that might have been shared by the author of the *Devi Gita* even though he does

not signal so textually. Certainly the Mahadevi is called Śakti already in the *Devī-Māhātmya*, which lends support to the hypothesis that the author of *Devi Gita* did not intend to completely exclude Śakti from Brahman/Maya, as though she would be a by-product of the creation of Śiva, or somehow a new force entirely. Clearly she must have existed as a potentiality within Brahman/Maya, to say the least, and, if one assumes that hers is the creative power to bring potentiality into fulfilment, saying that Śakti existed as a potentiality within Brahman/Maya equals saying that she was the potentiality of potentialities, the inversion of the *regressus ad infinitum*, the infinite power to bring nothingness into existence. In other words, the Womb of Wombs.

A Bengali Devi of childbirth and children is Jara, who in the *Mahabharata* is said to be a demoness who restored to life the two halves of the son of King Brihadatha of Magadha that had been born from his twin wives, thus being celebrated and worshipped as a Devi. The child was named Jarasandha in her honour, which means ‘the two halves joined by Jara’ (Ganguli 1973: 39-42). This kind of Devis are all Śaktis from the One Supreme Śakti, and they help in childmaking and childraising by the power of the very power from which the whole universe came to light: Womb of Wombs.

Another Bengali Devi of children and childbirth, Shashthi, is called Jatamatr [mother of the born one] in Banabhatta's 7th century *Harshacharita*, while the same author in his *Kadambari* calls her Bahuputrika [she who has many children]. Originating as a folk goddess, Shashthi was progressively assimilated into the Brahmanical Hindu pantheon, and eventually, became in Hinduism the Supreme Goddess and Mother of All (Singh 2000: 861-872). Shashthi's transformations are a parallel of those of the demoness Jara of the *Mahabharata*: from devourers of children these divinities become their protectors. The connection between Manasa and Shashthi is described by White in connection with their association with Śakti, “female energy in the yogic body.”

In Bengal, where her cult is particularly prominent, Śaṣṭhī is worshiped as a birdheaded goddess and is portrayed together with anywhere from one to eight infants. There she is also closely associated with Manasā, the Serpent Goddess, a most archaic pairing that is elsewhere represented in an illuminated Nepalese Sanskrit manuscript inspired by the medical classic the *Suśruta Saṃhitā*, in which all of the nine Seizers, of which several are bird-headed, have the bodies of serpents. There may also be a connection here with the later depiction of female energy in the yogic body, now as a serpent (*kuṇḍalinī*) and now as a bird (*hamsa*). (White 2003: 40-43)

This is a clear advocacy of the connection between the tantric practices and childmaking, which do not need to be absolute alternatives. On the contrary, the more one is united to the Devi through the practice of Yoga and Tantra, the more one gets to share in the infinite creativity of the first spring from which everything comes, and becoming like her one is filled with the same creativity that brings to life and raises children, sustains one in their professional activities, and delights one in the production and reception of artworks. We are all children in the arms of the Devi, but she is a child too, being celebrated as Kanya Puja during the Navratri festival in Northern India and as Kumari Puja in the parallel Durga Puja in East India. In the Lalita Sahasranama, it is reported that “according to *Devi Bhag. Or.*, a girl or right years is called Sambhu” (Sastry 1925: 98). So, let us all remember what it felt like when everything was new and a perpetual discovery, and let us all join the Devi in a playful game of hide and seek, there, in some lost garden of childhood, when we were still so close to the Womb of Wombs that we could feel, so we think, her very touch on our skin.

The Spouse of Her Son

Śiva is made the messenger of Candika in the *Devī-Māhātmya*, when the Devi challenges the Asuras Sumbha and Nisumbha to battle (*Devī-Māhātmya* 88.22-23, 26-27). Thomas Coburn comments by pointing out that Śakti produces her own Śakti, Śivaduti, like all other divinities (Coburn 1984: 138). Śiva is subdued by the Devi because he is her husband, but also because he is her son. The usage of his name as a name of the Devi does not need to be puzzling in this sense, even though Coburn seems confused.

That Śiva is the Devi's son cannot be doubted. In the *Devi Bhagavata Purana* Śiva exclaims: "O Auspicious Mother! It is Thou in the shape of Brahma, Vishnu and Śiva, That art creating this Universe and it is Thou that hast assumed the form of this whole Universe, moving non-moving. Thus Thou playest, as it wills Thee, under various forms, again and again. Thou dost cease from play (during *pralaya*) as it likes Thee" (Vijayanand 2011: 173).

In the *Lalita Sahasranama*, Sambhavi is both the wife of Śiva and the mother of his devotees (Sastry 1925: 98). Parvati is also called Tripura. In the *Tripura Rahasya* the Devi is defined as the consciousness of the Deva, in which his very nature consists. In other words, the Deva is fundamentally the Devi. This means that the relationship between an incarnate Deva and an incarnate Devi is subordinated to the Divine Consciousness that is the Supreme Devi. In other words, a Deva's marriage with the Devi or a Deva's filiation by the Devi are only different ways to express the same notion that every concept or perception exists within the Devi (Saraswathi 2002: 46-47).

It is important to recall that the Devi's body (or bodies) were described in detail in *Devi Gita*, all of unsurpassed beauty. In the same way, in the *Devī-Māhātmya*, the Devi is described as "exceedingly beautiful," thanks to whom Viṣṇu, Śiva, and Brahma were "made to assume bodily form," that is, were born. In *Devī-Māhātmya* it is not a matter of mirrors and conceiving ideas, but an actual pregnancy, like the one from which Parvati was born in *Devi Gita* (Coburn 1991: 37-38).

To be sure, the *Tripura Rahasya* does qualify the relationship between the Devi and Śiva in conjugal terms, and, even though the reference to consciousness as the underlying significance is still made, their union is said to be "concrete." The issue is definitely with the Advaita approach that characterizes this text.

My concrete form is the eternal couple—the Supreme Lord and Energy—always in undivided union and abiding as the eternal consciousness pervading the three phenomenal states of waking, dream and sleep, and reclining on the cot whose four legs are Brahmā (the Creator), Vishnu (the Protector), Śiva (the Destroyer) and Isvara (Disappearance) and whose surface is Sadasiva (Grace) which is contained in the mansion known as 'fulfilment of purpose' enclosed by the garden of 'Kadamba' trees in the jewel island situated in the wide ocean of nectar surrounding the cosmos and extending beyond. (Saraswathi 2002: 149)

The Devi is also conceived as Prakṛti, that is, Nature, generally considered to be a product of Brahman and associated with Maya under a negative judgment, but Prakṛti is elevated to the rank of Supreme Goddess in Śaktism. A comment by Shashibhusan Dasgupta clarifies in which sense the Trimurti are called sons of the Devi: "The three gunas of Prakṛti as conceived in the Samkhya system were ascribed to Śakti in the Tantric texts, and we frequently find that the triad, viz., Brahma, Visnu and Śiva, who are put in the charge of creation, preservation and destruction, are the three sons of the original Śakti; and they are of the nature of the three gunas, viz., *sattva* [harmony], *rajas* [passion] and *tamas* [inactivity]" (Dasgupta 1946: 387). According to the *Maha-bhagavata*, Prakṛti created the first goddess herself, who then created the Trimurti. Compared to *Tripura Rahasya*, this text admits a major role for a feminine personal Devi before any male Deva was born, but still conceives of the Absolute as impersonal,

feminine by analogy, whereas actual femininity is a subsequent product of this fundamental Prakṛti, subsequent even though it precedes every masculinity.

In the *Maha-bhagavata* we find that in the beginning the universe was without the sun and the moon; there was neither the day nor the night, nor fire nor the directions,—the whole universe was without touch, sight and sound, etc., and it was bereft of all the luminaries. At that time there was only Prakṛti as the supreme reality. When there was the desire for creation in her, she, though formless, assumed the form of a goddess and at once created a personality with the three *gunas* she had within her; but the person (Purusa) was without consciousness. She then infused her own creative impulse in that Purusa and the Purusa thus endowed with power created three personalities of the name of Brahma, Visnu and Śiva, who were of the nature of the three *gunas*. (Dasgupta 1946: 387)

As in my dream tradition, the Goddess pre-exists to everything as the Fatherless Daughter, but in kissing the God she creates him as her Spouse, Son, and Father, so becoming herself Spouse and Mother. In the same way, Prakṛti creates the three Devas of the Trimurti, but in order to do so she must become their Mother (Purusa) and Spouse (Shakti). There is also a witness to the egg of the world in another text that assumes her begetting of Śiva: “In the *Bahvrcopanisat* (which, however, is undoubtedly a text of much later time) it is said that in the beginning was the Goddess (Devi); she created the egg of the world,—and from her were born the gods like Brahma, Visnu and Śiva” (Dasgupta 1946: 380).

Bengali mystic Ramakrishna Paramahansa (1836-1886) holds the Absolute to be both Brahman and Śakti:

When I think of the Supreme Being as inactive – neither creating nor preserving nor destroying – I call Him Brahman or Purusha, the Impersonal God. When I think of Him as active – creating, preserving, and destroying – I call Him Śakti or Maya or Prakṛti, the Personal God. But the distinction between them does not mean a difference. The Personal and the Impersonal are the same thing, like milk and its whiteness, the diamond and its lustre, the snake and its wriggling motion. It is impossible to conceive of the one without the other. The Divine Mother and Brahman are one. (Gupta 1942: 44)

In Shṛīyukta Śiva Chandra Vidyārnava Bhattachāryya Mahodaya’s *Tantra Tattva* the god Brahma asks the Devi how can she be hymned when she is everything, when the Trimurti comes from her, when she sent even Brahman to sleep:

O Thou who art all things, how canst Thy greatness be hymned when Thou art the Shakti in everything, *asat* [unconscious] or *sat* [conscious], which is anywhere in the world? Who can hymn Thee by whom even Bhagavan, the creator, preserver, and destroyer of the world, has been overcome through sleep? From Thee, Vishnu, Myself, and Ishana [Śiva] have derived our bodies. Who is, therefore, capable of making hymn to Thee who art the origin of even Brahma and others? Devi of unspeakable power, Thy own vast powers be praised. (Avalon 1952: 409)

In Bengal one finds many instances of worship of the Devi Chinnamastika, depicted in statues as a self-beheading naked maiden from whose severed throat three rivulets of blood spring to be drunk by two female attendants and her own severed head. She is shown standing or seated upon the copulating Divine Couple. Chinnamastika is the Virgin, the Absolute from whom the Divine Couple arises, the Fatherless Daughter, but also the Womb of Wombs, the Mother, feeding her children from her own body.

Harsha V. Dehejia comments on the union of Śiva and Śakti that it is a biune experience, which is true, but only because both masculine and feminine derive from the Eternal Feminine:

It is well to remind ourselves of the words of Sri Aurobindo that Prakāśa and Vimarśa, Śiva and Vimarśini Pārvati, Cit and Cit-Śakti, Ānanda and Hladini-Śakti, *jnāna* and *kriyā* "are really not something dual and separate, it is biune." "In the superconscious truth ... these two are fused and implied in each other, one and indistinguishable, but in the spiritual- pragmatic truth of the dynamism of the universe, they emerge and become active." This concept of Pārvati vimarsini, beautifully depicted by Ardhanārīsvara, is ideally suited to the understanding of the whole of all experience but particularly aesthetic experience. An aesthete encounters and utilises the sensuous and beautiful art object, which is none other than Parvati incarnate in leading him to a transcendent experience, and in that experience loses nothing of Pārvati as he gains Siva. In the concept of Abhinavaguptā, Parvati is more than a mere consort or "Mother Goddess" but a "Vimarsini" for the artist, aesthete and the seeker of Brahman. (Dehejia 1993: 231)

Kali trampling on Śiva's body is a typical image that reminds one of the divine superiority of women to men, in a way that is difficult to accept for many Westerners and also for many Indians.

In an influential chapter of *The Divine Consort*, Frederique Apffel Marglin discussed the meanings of different patterns of sexual union between gods and goddesses, as seen through the eyes of women she interviewed in Puri, Orissa. Three patterns emerge. In one, the male is dominant and is often portrayed as larger than the woman; in another, the two sexes are equal and are often equal in size; in the third, the female prevails and is often shown larger than the male, or above him. The first is typified by the relation between Visnu and his consort Laksmi (or Sri); the second is illustrated in the love of Radha and Krishna; and the third is archetypally present in the union between Śiva and Kali. (Hawley 1995: 14)

In *Linga Purana*, one reads that once Parvati breastfed Lord Śiva in the form of Kali. As the Devas came to Śiva for help with the Asura Daruka, Śiva asked Parvati to destroy the demon. Upon his request, she took the form of Kali and annihilated Darukasura. However, her anger did not dissipate even after the demon was destroyed, and the whole universe trembled before the unleashing of her fury. Then Śiva took a child's form to soothe her. Pacified by the Māyā of Śiva, Kali saw the boy and started breastfeeding him, in the process reverting to her previous form as the peaceful Parvati (Shastri 1970: 579-581).

The tale just told is another clear indicator that the Devi is the Spouse of Her Son. This is not a mere abstraction meant to convey a mystical sense of the divinity of consciousness underlying every (divine) manifestation. This is a witness to actual divine persons. The explanation of this mystery that is found in the *Tripura Rahasya* is a praiseworthy attempt at clarification that nonetheless is objectionable in its Advaita approach, too riskful in daring to attempt utter clarity: revelation, etymology says, means covering with a new veil, not uncovering, because truth unveiled is false, and it is only truth revealed that is true. Nakedness is made for lovers, not for scientific observers. But assistance can be provided by helpful hands. The sense of a revelation can be revealed anew. Goddess may appear again in a new garment. Let us then follow in the trail of Bengal and their rich tradition of Devi worship. Let us all be handmaids and servants of the Devi and assist her as she changes her dress.

Dinesh Chandra Sen highlights how Bengali literature, as witnessed by the poems addressed to Manasa Devi and Chandi Devi, testifies to just such a preference for a personal deity over an impersonal divine force, and especially a feminine personal deity.

The propaganda of the Sakta cult, however, was to restore faith in a personal divinity in the place of the impersonal Siva. All through these poems one is sure to find the mother's heart in the divinities, eager to stretch out protecting hands to those children that cling to them. Into whatever danger a believer may fall, he cries out for the motherly help of the divinity whom he worships in a patient and prayerful spirit, and she is sure to appear to him with anxious solicitude to protect

him. Instances of this personal element in the deities are to be found throughout the literature of the Saktas. The characters of Srimanta and Kalketu in *Chandi Kavya*, of Sundara in *Vidya Sundara*, of Lau Sen in *Dharma Mangal*, as recast by the Hindu priests, and of Behula in *Manasa Mangal*, have been all depicted as attaining great success in life by force of their devotion alone. When all resources failed and the great characters were reduced to utmost straits—some of them being doomed to die on the scaffold, they fixed their whole heart on the mother and solicited divine help with tearful eyes, despairing of saving themselves by their own power, and the mother was sure to come to her devotees stretching out the hand of succour. (Sen 1954: 232)

Sen is referring to the Bengali legend of the Serpent Goddess Manasa and Chand Sanagar, the devotee of Śiva. Manasa wished that she could be a major goddess like Parvati or Sri Lakshmi. In order to achieve this goal, she had to be worshipped by Chand Sadagar, who had taken an oath to worship only Śiva. Manasa tried to convert him by scaring him and so she destroyed his garden, but he revived it thanks to the Maha Jnan power that he had gotten from Śiva. Manasa seduced him in the form of a beautiful maiden and convinced him to give her his power, then she destroyed his garden again, but Chand had a friend who also had Maha Jnan and he restored the garden. Manasa killed this friend of his and destroyed his garden again, but still he would not worship her. Then Manasa killed his six sons, but even then she did not succeed in shaking his resolve. Eventually, Manasa conspired against Lakshmindara, Chand and Sanaka's seventh son, who was bitten by a snake and died on the day of his wedding with the beautiful Behula. Praying Manasa, Behula floated on water for nine months with the corpse of her husband and reached the abode of the Gods, where she danced so well that they conceded her to get her husband's life back. However, Manasa protested that she had to convert her father-in-law before getting Lakshmindara back, which Behula did upon her return to the house of Chand. At last, Chand offered a flower to the Devi with his left hand without even looking at her. This gesture gladdened Manasa so much that she brought back to life all of Chand's sons and restored his peace and prosperity (Sen 1954: 233-249).

Coomaraswamy and Nivedita comment by confirming the same account as that provided by Sen in the quotation above:

This legend of Manasa Devi, the goddess of snakes, who must be as old as the Mykenean stratum in Asiatic culture, reflects the conflict between the religion of Shiva and that of feminine local deities in Bengal. Afterwards Manasa or Padma was recognized as a form of Shakti (does it not say in the *Mahabharata* that all that is feminine is a part of Uma?), and her worship accepted by the Shaivas. She is a phase of the mother-divinity who for so many worshippers is nearer and dearer than the far-off and impersonal Shiva... (Coomaraswamy and Nivedita 1967: 330)

As Sen says, “But what do the followers of Śiva gain as the reward for their heroic devotion to his cause? The great Śiva passive and inert, cares not for the sufferings of his followers” (Sen 1954: 217). The past conflict between Śaktism and Śaivism tells us that the claim of the Devi worshippers of a Supreme Goddess and personal feminine Goddesses acting as daughters, spouses, and mothers were met with strong opposition because they were perceived as a threat to patriarchal structures of power. In terms of my tradition, it is the conflict between Goddess and First Patriarch.

It is important to recall how in these legends Śiva loses his senses by swallowing poison and then Śiva is restored to his senses by Manasa who sucks the poison out of his mouth and spits it out. So Manasa can also be depicted in a superior position to Śiva, his rescuer, his savior. Although Manasa is called a daughter of Śiva, as already seen, and one of his wives, she can also be thought of as his mother in her being Śakti. The contrast between her supreme power in the legend of Chand and Śiva's ineptitude lends credit to the idea. Exactly as Parvati in the

Devi Gita, she would be the mother of her own father and spouse, which is coherent with my dream tradition.

The devotion of Behula to both the Devi and her husband is another key point mirroring the fidelity of the Supreme Goddess. Behula lamented her lost Lakshmindara before leaving with his corpse on the river to reach the abode of the Gods in Narayana Deva's poem dedicated to the Goddess Manasa:

Where art thou gone, my lord, without me? Awake beloved, lift up thine eyes and look upon thy Behula. Alas, that beauty which shone so bright, putting the sun and moon to shame, has been stolen away by the bite of Kali, the snake. My Sari of silk must now be tom off, my bracelets of shell must now be broken, and I, unfortunate that I am, must wipe off the vermilion from my forehead. Oh my lord! how long will you sleep? Will you not wake and speak, to me? Will you not look again at my face? Oh! what fault have I committed against you, that you should make me wretched forever! To whose care have you left your miserable Behula? (Sen 1954: 255-256)

The lamentation of Behula recalls one of the 52 pieces into which the first wife of Śiva, Sati, was dismembered when the God carried her dead body on his back unleashing his fury. Sati was not revived but reincarnated as Parvati who also married Śiva, although she had to relentlessly court him before he agreed. Even here the very Śiva cannot stand the comparison with Behula, a simple mortal who believes in Manasa Devi: she manages to restore to life her beloved, while he has to wait for her to reincarnate, and forgets her meanwhile. The Devi is superior to Śiva both as mother and spouse.

There is a little known variant of the widespread legend of Tansen singing the Deepak Rags in an Hindu story of three singers that is also concerned with magical songs and represents an instance of Thompson motif E55.1. Resuscitation by song:

Now I am going to tell you a story, and everyone must pay attention with all his ears. Once on a day the Emperor Akbar went out hunting with Birbal, Faizi, and all the rest of his retinue. They found nothing to chase, and as it was the hot month of Jeth, they rested under the shade of a large banyan tree. As they rested there, the Emperor commanded Faizi to sing something, and he sung so sweetly that all the wild beasts of the forests,—the deer, the hares, the jackals and so forth—came to listen, and stood before him, with their eyes closed in ecstasy, and utterly devoid of consciousness. One deer stood with its face close up to Faizi, and he took off his rosary and threw it round her neck. The action broke the charm, and the animals each took their own way to the forest. When Akbar sat next day in court Faizi was absent owing to a severe attack of fever; but Birbal said, 'Your Majesty, Faizi has become inflated with pride, and thinks that no one can sing like him. Hence ho has not come to court, and will not come again.' Said the Emperor, 'but is there no other singer?' Replied Birbal, 'if Your Majesty gives the order, I can fetch Birju Baura.' 'Let him be summoned.' So Birbal fetched Birju Baura, and he began to sing. Then all the beasts of the forests came into the court, when they heard his song, and began to listen as before. Amongst them stood the deer on whose neck Faizi had thrown his rosary, and Birbal took it off her neck, and cast it before him. But Birju said, 'why are you praising me? Tan-sen can sing better than even I.' So the Emperor summoned Tan-sen, and he began to sing the Melody of Illumination. He sang with such tire that all the lamps in the room lit themselves, and he himself burst into flames and fell down dead. He had, however, warned them beforehand that, should he die, they should lay his corpse secretly in the moat of the fort of Chittaur, and set men to guard it to prevent its being devoured by wild beasts. Then, when Queen Kamla of Chittaur should lustrate her husband with lamps on the fifth of the month of Sawan, and should sing the Melody of Mallar, he would come to life. The Emperor carried out these instructions, and, when the queen began to sing, Tan-sen came to life, and clapped his hands in time to the music. When she heard him beating time, she knew that Tan-sen had heard her singing. In the meantime he rose up, and fled

to the Emperor, who declared that he must hear Queen Kamla sing. He marched forth and attacked Chittaur, and such a terrible battle ensued that of the brahmanical threads of Brahmans and Kshatriyas alone, they collected seventy-four and a half maunds. This very number, 74½, people still write at the head of a letter to prevent anybody opening it. When the Raja of Chittaur fell in the battle, and his army was defeated, the Emperor took Queen Kamla prisoner, and had her carried in a litter to his own city. There he gave the order, that her song would be heard on the following morning in full court. Next morning she appeared, and, taking her lute, raised her voice to the Melody of Prosperity. As she did so, her soul burst its way through her skull, and went to heaven, while all her audience remained seated where they were, with their mouths open in astonishment. (Grierson 1904: 48-49)

There is a tale in the Hindi *Mahabharata* (Kincaid 1918: 47-50), wherein Ruru and Pramadvara feature as a happy couple until a snake bites her leg and she dies. Ruru is griefstricken and summons the God of Death Yama, telling him that there is nothing that he would not do in order to have Pramadvara brought back to him. Yama tells him that he will restore her to life for the length of half Ruru's years, provided that he sacrifices the same amount of his own lifetime. Ruru agrees and he and Pramadvara get back happily together for the rest of their years. Hultkranz also relates how "[a] celebrated episode in *Mahabharata* describes how the beautiful Savitri, married to the exiled prince Satyavant, was deprived of her husband by Yama, the god of death. She followed him, however, and did not return until he had restored her father-in-law's kingdom and the life of her husband" (Hultkranz 2022: 190). There are also in Bengali traditions "the bewailings of Raiti, the wife of Madan (full of tender pathos: 'Let the years that I might live be added to your life, my dear husband, do you live for ever letting me die here at your feet')" (Sen 1954: 302).

On a symbolical level, it is the Mother of Her Spouse who can bring him back to life, because she already gave birth to him and so she can give him rebirth.

The notion of conception and birth through a kiss that one finds in my dream tradition finds a perfect explanation in the Tantras:

[According to Tantras], "the secret channel of access to the siddhis consists of the Five Streams." This term, the Five Streams or Five Currents (*pañcasrotas*), is in fact the earliest term that one encounters in the Śaivāgamas for the lines of transmission of that tradition's teachings. In these sources the five streams or currents are said to flow from the five mouths of the god Śiva. Later, Kaula traditions would posit a sixth mouth, called the "nether mouth" or "mouth of the Yoginī," the source of its teachings and clan lineages, from which a sixth current streamed. This is called the *picuvaktra* ("cotton mouth"), whence the name by which the Brahmayāmala calls itself in its colophons: Picumata, the "Doctrine of the [Nether] Cotton Mouth." We have already postulated that the mouth—and particularly the nether mouth—of the Tantric Yoginī was not her oral cavity, but rather her vulva. (White 2003: 99-100)

While White claims that the kiss of the Yoginī which provides the title to his work is actually the *cunnilingus* form of oral sex, the dream tradition that I received insists that genital sex, the *lingam-yoni* of the Tantras, the key in the lock of my dream tradition, is the highest manifestation of the Divine. That childmaking, when things work as they should, proceeds from this kind of union is indicative of its creative power reflecting the Goddess's powers of Creation. Furthermore, it is stated in the dream tradition, this union, by wielding the same power as Creation, works magic, the equivalent of the Siddhis, transforming the spouses into an enlightened couple blessed with miraculous powers of divination and healing to open the way to immortality. However, the fact that in the tradition the Goddess defines the key in the lock as the highest form of sexual union in and by itself implies that the other forms of sex such as oral, anal, etc., are also licit and pleasurable.

In the sixth chapter of the *Caṇḍamahāroṣaṇatantra* one reads about the sexual union between the Yogi and the Yogini as it takes the form of anal sex, and in this context the Yogini is both the Yogi's consort and his mother:

In front of him, looking him in the face, she should scratch him wherever appropriate. She should speak to him in this way: "Eat my Vairocana! Drink the Akṣobhya-water, O Son! Be a slave along with your father! I am your cow-girl as well as your royal mother. Constantly take refuge at my feet, my dear. You were raised by me, hence your invaluable nature." (Grimes and Szántó 2018)

In Mahāsukhavajra's *Padmāvātī* commentary on the sixth chapter of the *Caṇḍamahāroṣaṇatantra* one finds an explanation of the obscure references and the significance of the Yogini's motherhood:

Then the yoginī should make the yogī lay down, facing upwards. Then she should place her anal lotus and her vaginal lotus in front of his mouth, recite the three syllables, and say Eat Vairocana! and so forth. [Then] she should quickly give [those substances to him] as she pleases. Vairocana means faeces. Akṣobhya-water means urine. As for the yogī, he should take all that with reverence, become still [for a few minutes], and contemplate nothing but the pleasure [derived from ingestion]. Then she should make him rise once again and address [him the words] beginning with [Be a slave] along with your father. [Now for the passage] beginning with By me. [You] have been brought up by me, assuming the shape of [your] mother, in your childhood with breast milk etc. [Hence your] invaluable, [that is to say,] priceless [nature, i.e. present state]. The implied meaning is [that by this fostering the yogī has assumed] a distinguished state. (Grimes and Szántó 2018)

In another passage from the sixth chapter of the *Caṇḍamahāroṣaṇatantra* one also finds that the Yogini of the Yogi is his mother in the context of anal sex:

Again, having her assume the "Bow" seat, he should have his face fall in the middle of her anus. He should also stroke her anus with his nose. He should contemplate the pleasure produced by that in [meditative] union [with Caṇḍa[mahā]roṣaṇa]. Then the yogī should be liberated, with all predilections abandoned. Making his mind devoid of aversion, he should make love to his mother. (Grimes and Szántó 2018)

Mahāsukhavajra's *Padmāvātī* commentary explains: "Also with his nose means he should breathe in the odour after having placed his nose there. [. . .] [His] mother means the consort defined above" (Grimes and Szántó 2018). These practices are usually restricted to the Kaulas and Aghoris and do not constitute the rule among Tantrics, not to say Hindus or Buddhists.

In another passage the notion of the Spouse of Her Son is made explicit, as the Yogini says to the Yogi: "You are my son and my husband; you are my brother and father. I am your mother, wife, sister, and niece. Together with seven generations of your paternal ancestors, you are my slave, my phlegm-eating lowly servant. I bought you with cowrie shells; I am called your mistress" (Grimes and Szántó 2018). The Yogi replies to her: "You are my mother, my father's wife, and you are my niece. You are my sister, my son's wife, you are my paternal aunt and maternal aunt. I am your slave in all ways, keenly active in devotion to you. O Mother, look upon me with kindness, casting a loving glance" (Grimes and Szántó 2018).

The aforecited Ramakrishna is reported to practice Tantras and worshipping his wife as the Divine Mother. During his priesthood, Ramakrishna performed the rite called Shodashi Puja in his room, worshipping his wife Sarada Devi as the Divine Mother herself. Ramakrishna saw Sarada as the Devi

in person, calling her Holy Mother, the very name by which she came to be known by his followers (Rolland 1929: 59).

Another Devi worshipped in Bengal is Shashthi, the deity of children, childbirth, and fertility. In the texts, Shashthi is often portrayed as closely connected to Skanda, the son of Śiva. During the 8th–9th century BCE Shashthi was connected to the six Krittikas who took care of Skanda. She is sometimes regarded as an aspect of Durga Devi, who is identified with Parvati mother of Skanda, even being called Skandamata [Skanda's mother] (Stutley 2003: 127). *Yajnavalkya Smṛiti* describes Shashthi as the foster-mother and protector of Skanda (Naraharaya 2008). Nonetheless, in later texts she is identified with Devasena, the consort of Skanda (Bhattacharij 1998: 66), for example in the epic *Mahabharata* wherein Indra betroths Shashthi (called Devasena) to Skanda. In the *Mahabharata* Shashthi is also identified with the Devi Shri Lakshmi. The *Padma Purana* also describes Shashthi as the wife of Skanda (White 2003: 40-43; Singh 2000: 861-872).

Shashthi is another form of the Devi through whom the mystery appears of the Spouse of Her Son.

Conclusions

It has been proven how fruitful can be the comparison between a personal tradition that was offered to me in a dream and the beliefs of Bengali Śaktism. Three interconnected concepts shaping my tradition are consistent with Bengali Śaktism. In the first place, the Devi as Fatherless Daughter is a concept that may be observed in *Devi Gita*, since Parvati is incarnated as the daughter of the Mountain Lord and his Queen even though she is everything and timeless. It was said that the Devi generated the Father already in Hymn 125 in Book 10 of the *Rig Veda*. The Serpent Goddess Manasa's birth, either from the head of a sage or from a girl's statue on which Śiva's seed fell, also testifies to the Devi's fatherless daughterhood. The sixth chapter of the *Caṇḍamahāroṣaṇatantra* and Mahāsukhavajra's *Padmāvati* commentary explain the identity of Mother and Daughter as two candidates for the same role of Tantric Yogini.

In the *Devi Gita* one also finds the Devi as Womb of Wombs, since Parvati ties Yoga practice with inter-uterine life. Bhāskararāya's commentary to *Devī-Māhātmya* highlights the very notion of Brahman as one with Śakti against which the author of *Devi Gita* appears to object, but he could not have left unconsidered a concept of Mahaśakti as the Womb of Wombs. Matron deities of children like Manasa, Shashthi, and Jara are subject to intense worship in Bengal, and, in their coming from Śakti, they also stand for the Womb of Wombs.

The Devi as Spouse of Her Son is apparent in *Devī-Māhātmya*, in *Devi Bhagavata Purana*, and in *Tripura Rahasya*, even though the latter text adheres to an Advaita Vedanta approach that might be objectionable. In *Tantra Tattva* and *Maha-bhagavata* one finds the concept of Śiva as the Devi's son as much as her Spouse. In the *Linga Purana*, Parvati the wife of Śiva in her Kali form is still furious after killing an Asura for him, and Śiva manages to soothe her by appearing to her as a child and being breastfed by her.

The Bengali legend of Manasa and Chand represents the fight between Śaivism and Śaktism stemming from Śaivist contrast to the notion and worship of the Highest Devi, but they never managed to suppress the Śaktic faith, even though they could force some restraint to the Devi's affirmation, censoring those who preached Śiva's filiation from the Devi as well as those who claimed her being Mother, Spouse, and Daughter, so to enforce rationalist abstractions instead of the happy enjoyment of earthly existence. The Mother of Her Spouse is explained in the sixth chapter of the *Caṇḍamahāroṣaṇatantra* and Mahāsukhavajra's *Padmāvati* commentary as the sex partner who initiates the Tantric Yogi into the mysteries of sex, including oral and anal performances

I conclude by quoting from my unpublished writings. Praise be to the Goddess, whose boons are plentiful.

“The Goddess keeps the sweetest memories in a special treasure chest of her heart, ready to be opened only by those with the right key. She recalls the blooming of the first orchid and the blossoming of the first buttercup, the first song of a nightingale and the first blush on a girl's cheeks.”

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